

FloodForT – User Manual

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Overview

The **Flood Forecasting Toolbox** is a series of routines implemented in the R statistical computing language (Ihaka and Gentleman, 1996) designed to aid the implement a simplified hydrological real time forecasting strategy for the prediction of floods. The main component of the toolbox ModelBuild is a GUI for building the forecasting models from observed data. The functions contained within the package and used by ModelBuild can then reused in real time operation situations. However since the implementation of operational systems is highly dependent upon local requirements this use is not discussed further. Details of the software installation can be found in the Installation Guide. This manual outlines

1. The basis of the simplified hydrological real time forecasting strategy
2. The format of the text (ascii) data files used to for data input and output
3. The usage of the ModelBuild GUI associated with the toolbox

Details of the computational schemes and technical software details are omitted though further details may be found in the help files for the FloodForT package. Details of the hydrological models and their estimation are found in FloodForT methodology section below.

The FloodForT methodology

Operational flood forecasting has become a complex and multifaceted task. This section outlines the approach taken to flood forecasting in the FloodForT toolbox which is based upon the Data Based Mechanistic (DBM) modelling methodology utilised in Young (2002) and many of the references below. The methodology used in FloodForT follows the increasingly popular trend of treating the forecasting problem in probabilistic way to allow for the inherent uncertainties in the forecasting process. The off-line calibration and validation of the models is discussed along with the on-line adaptive implementation in which real time data is assimilated to improve the forecasts

Model Outline

The ability to issue flood warnings in a timely manner is an important part of mitigating the impact of flooding. In modern flood management practice the issuing of warnings is guided by numerical models for forecasting future water levels or discharge. While 1 and 2 dimensional hydrodynamic models of flood inundation are useful for management and planning purposes, to issue warnings it is often adequate to forecast only at specific points of interest where observations (either of water level or discharge) are available to evaluate the model forecasts. Extension to other river reaches where the risk of overtopping defences is significant is then generally related to different threshold warning levels at the forecast site.

The methodology used within FloodForT produces forecasts at locations with observations based on time series models derived from available data. The models used are a form of Data Based Mechanistic (DBM) model (Young 2002). They are parsimonious time series models that can be interpreted in a mechanistic or hydrological fashion (see for example Young and Beven 1994; Young 2001, 2002, 2003). These models are combined with an efficient data assimilation strategy to produce probabilistic forecasts of future observations.

Applicability

There are essentially two types of flood warning situation. The first type is where the natural response time of a catchment is insufficient to allow warnings with an adequate lead time to be based on rainfall measurements alone. In this case, both early warnings and event-time-scale warnings are necessarily dependent on rainfall forecasts, either extrapolated from radar rainfall fields (often called Quantitative Precipitation Forecasts, QPF) or from numerical weather prediction (NWP) models. In both cases, ensembles of rainfall predictions may be available.

The second is where the natural response time of a catchment is sufficient to allow a short-term warning with useful lead time to be issued during an event. In this case, the short term warning could depend only on rain gauge or radar rainfall data (Quantitative Precipitation Estimates, QPE). It might also be possible to make use of measured river flow or level data for real-time updating of the forecasts. This will generally only be the case for forecast points in larger catchments, but the use of data assimilation might then be highly valuable for accuracy in the prediction of new events. In this second type of situation, rainfall forecasts will then be more useful in early warning / flood alert decisions with the longer lead times required.

While DBM modelling can be used for the first type (Smith and Beven 2010; Alfieri et al. 2011; Smith et al. 2011) it is ideally suited to the second of these types since, as outlined in the following sections, the hydrologically interpretable model can be readily expressed in a state space form that

allows robust data assimilation using linear filtering techniques. It is this situation that is considered below.

Representation of uncertainties in the flood forecast process

At a governmental level it has been acknowledged that accurate warning at a specific location

“...can probably only be aspirational in some cases due to the uncertainty and complexity of natural systems such as rainfall and water flow.” (Penning-Rowsell, E. et al. 2008 Paragraph 20.30)

and that

“There is some evidence that the public is more tolerant of uncertainty which has been honestly admitted than is often believed, and acknowledging uncertainty often carries fewer dangers.” (Penning-Rowsell et al. 2008 Paragraph 20.12; Frewer et al. 1996)

To acknowledge uncertainty in flood forecasts requires recognition of both the sources of the uncertainty and how they are handled in the forecasting process. Such information offers a starting point for the use of uncertainty representations within the frameworks for flood response.

There are a number of different sources of uncertainty. In particular we may identify:

1. uncertainty in observed rainfall fields, only partially captured by interpolation of raingauge data and calibration of radar data;
2. uncertainty in antecedent conditions, only partially captured by running hydrological models continuously;
3. uncertainty in model structures in representing runoff generation and routing processes;
4. uncertainty in calibration of model parameters, only partially captured by estimation of parameter distributions and their dependence on uncertainty in observations used in model calibration or data assimilation (which may be particularly high at flood levels);

The modelling framework used in FloodForT addresses these sources of uncertainty in a number of ways. The first two sources are addressed through the use of noise terms in the data assimilation scheme which are designed to reflect the error in the evolution of the model states. This term also compensates for inadequacy in the model structure and uncertainty in the calibration of the model. The deductive method of model selection (see the following section) allows for the exploration of potential model structures, albeit that in operational forecasting only one structure is utilised while the fourth source is treated by the implementation of models within a stochastic parameter and error framework.

The methodology we propose is equally capable of forecasting water levels directly rather than estimates of discharge (see also Beven et al. 2008, 2011a; Leedal et al. 2008; Romanowicz et al. 2008). This reduces the effects of rating curve uncertainties at gauged sites but clearly such models cannot be constrained by mass balance. This can actually be an advantage for flood forecasting, when we do not necessarily expect to have good knowledge of rainfall input data from either raingauges or radar, and where rating curves may be extrapolated well beyond the range of available measurements.

Data requirements

Table 1 outlines the minimum data requirements for the constructions of a FloodForT model representing a rainfall-water level relationship. Similar data periods are required for a model representing flood routing driven by an observed upstream water level. Higher temporal resolution in the data (e.g. 5 minutes) may be of use in some catchments.

Table 1: Data requirements for the DBM methodology to be applied in a catchment (Minimal Data requirements in BOLD)

Variable	Time step	Time period
Precipitation	15 minutes, 1 hour	10 significant events , 5+ years
Discharge or Water level	15 minutes, 1 hour	<i>10 significant events including baseflow periods</i> , 5+ years

Modelling is often possible using only rainfall records as inputs. Temperature may be required if snowmelt is a significant runoff generation mechanism (Young et al. 2007; Smith et al. 2011) but further observations such as global radiation or wind speed are not required. Unlike most hydrological models there is no requirement for physiographical information (such as a digital terrain model or land surface characteristics) beyond readily available metadata such as catchment maps showing rain gauges and river connectivity.

Care should be taken in selecting and processing the data before modelling. Data should be representative of the current catchment dynamics and if possible represent the variability within the catchment (e.g. rain gauges at a range of elevations). The observed input and output data should be checked for consistency. Periods of data that display some inconsistency (e.g. high discharge and no rainfall, single time steps with high precipitation values but no runoff response) should be considered carefully since they might either represent important catchment dynamics or data of dubious quality that should not be included in the model calibration (Beven et al. 2011b). Changes in the water level during low flow periods that might be the result of changes in channel form during floods should also be noted since the rainfall-water level dynamics may not be well captured if they are not taken into account.

Building DBM forecast models

A number of papers (see Romanowicz et al. 2006, 2008; Beven et al. 2011a; Young 2006 and the references within) address the construction of types of Data Based Mechanistic models of hydrological systems 'offline' using historical data. The FloodForT toolbox is an application of these methodologies designed specifically for robust yet rapid application. This section summarises this work focusing upon the estimation of a model of the hydrological response at a single gauge (be it water level or discharge) using a single known input series (often a catchment average precipitation estimate or an upstream water level/discharge). Multiple input series are not currently supported by FloodForT except through their explicit combination using user defined weighting.

Before proceeding with details it is important to note that the philosophy behind the modelling used is not only that of fitting a model which is (in some predefined sense) statistically optimal and utilising this as a black box in forecasting. Instead, while fitted to optimise some criterion and maintain parsimony, a model must also have a mechanistic interpretation as a representation of the physical system. The parameterisations and structures utilised in FloodForT ensure that is the case

but the values of the parameters selected should always be checked against perceptual models of the system.

The foundation of the models used is the linear transfer function. Equation (1) describes a discrete time linear transfer function between the observed output $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_T)$ and input

$\mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_T)$, indexed by time, using the backward shift operator z^{-1} ($z^{-1}y_t = y_{t-1}$) where v is a constant offset, ε_t is a stochastic disturbance and t is the time step index. For the purposes of this paper we consider v to be indicative of a baseflow output value so that the remainder of the model characterises the supposition of the event hydrographs.

$$y_t - v = \frac{b_0 + b_1 z^{-1} + \dots + b_m z^{-m}}{1 + a_1 z^{-1} + \dots + a_n z^{-n}} u_{t-d} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

The structure of the model is defined by three positive integers. Two of these, m and n , are the order of the transfer function numerator and denominator polynomials respectively. The third d is number of time steps of pure, advective time delay. This limits the forecast lead time available from the observed input data.

The most common mechanistic interpretation of a linear transfer function seen in a flood forecasting context is that of parallel response paths. In this situation $m = n - 1$. For example a model with $(n, m) = (2, 1)$ can be decomposed using partial fractions to give:

$$\frac{b_0 + b_1 z^{-1}}{1 + a_1 z^{-1} + a_2 z^{-2}} = \frac{\beta_1}{1 + \alpha_1 z^{-1}} + \frac{\beta_2}{1 + \alpha_2 z^{-1}} \quad (2)$$

The first order terms represent two parallel tanks. These can be analysed in terms of their time constants ($\approx -\Delta t / \log(-\alpha_i)$ where Δt is the model time step) and steady state gains ($\beta_i / (1 + \alpha_i)$ which should be greater than zero) to ensure that they are consistent with the modeller's concept of the system response. Since it is reasonable to assume positive time constants and steady state gains the parameters restrictions

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < \alpha_i < 1 \\ \beta_i > 0 \end{aligned}$$

are imposed for all i during estimation.

In some situations a linear transfer function, coupled with data assimilation, may prove adequate for forecasting the future response of the system (see for example Lees et al. 1994). More commonly, the non-linear problems found in flood forecasting require the use of some additional model complexity. This usually takes the form of a non-linear transformation of the input signal. This transformation of the input is often dependent on the current state of the system. A convenient means of representing this transformation (Young and Beven 1994) is as a gain series

$\mathbf{f} = (f_1, \dots, f_T)$ allowing the resulting model to be expressed as

$$y_t - v = \frac{b_0 + b_1 z^{-1} + \dots + b_m z^{-m}}{1 + a_1 z^{-1} + \dots + a_n z^{-n}} f_{t-d} u_{t-d} + \eta_t \quad (3)$$

where η_t is a stochastic noise term. Models of this form, using a number of different methods to calculate \mathbf{f} have proved acceptable representations of a variety of catchments (see for example, Beven et al. 2011a, Young 2001; Ratto et al. 2007; Beven et al. 2005, 2008; Romanowicz et al. 2006, 2008; Leedal et al. 2008 and Smith et al. 2008, 2012a).

Within the FloodForT package two parametric descriptions of \mathbf{f} are available. These have been found to be suitable for many catchments but are known not to capture the dynamics of some situations such as snowfall. In such cases a simple physical model may be appropriate (e.g. the degree day model used to predict snowmelt inputs in Smith et al. 2011).

The first parametric description of the input non-linearity available is the power law where:

$$f_t = F(y_t, \varphi) = y_t^\varphi \quad 0 < \varphi < 1 \quad (4)$$

In this situation y_t is used as a surrogate for catchment wetness. Since f_t is strictly increasing as y_t increases it is presumed that higher flows represent wetter catchments. However the value of f_t converges asymptotically for increasing y_t producing an effect akin to a catchment becoming saturated. In fact under certain assumptions it can be shown theoretically that the value of φ in the power law is related to the distribution of the topographic index values utilised for example in TOPMODEL.

The second parametric description of the input non-linearity available is the negative exponential where:

$$f_t = F(y_t, \varphi) = \exp(-\varphi_1(y_t - \varphi_2)) \quad \varphi_1 > 0 \quad \min(y_t) < \varphi_1 < \max(y_t) \quad (4)$$

As for the power law y_t is used as a surrogate for catchment wetness and f_t is strictly increasing. However the functional form and additional parameter allow for greater flexibility in the location of the most rapid change in f_t and hence effective input for a unit of observed input. This can be useful in characterising catchments where there may be a distinct 'wetting up' phase before larger parts of the catchment start to respond.

Identification and estimation of the Model

Consider the identification and estimation of a hydrological model of the form outlined above.

Presuming v , if it is included, is well estimated by $\min_{t=1, \dots, T} (y_t)$ the remaining parameters to be

estimated are $\theta_{n,d,F} = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n, \varphi)$ where the subscript n, d, F denotes the selected number of parallel pathways of response, advective time delay and non-linear gain function. For a given combination (n, d, F) the parameters are estimated based upon the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) criteria

$$E \left[\frac{\partial \eta_t}{\partial \theta_{n,d,F}} \eta_t \right] = 0$$

This is consistent with the Refined Instrumental Variable (RIV) method introduced in Young (1976; see Young 2011 for a more recent description) widely used within DBM modelling for the estimation of linear transfer functions. To provide a robust estimation of the parameter covariance Σ when

the error series has unknown, possibly non-stationary and heteroscedastic, error properties the Heteroscedastic, Auto-covariance Consistent (HAC) estimator of Newey & West (1987) (see also Zeileis, 2004) is used.

A number of summary statistics of the model errors given in Table 2 are reported for the calibration and validation periods. Since model estimation is rapid it is suggested that an exhaustive search of the combinations of (n, d, F) is performed. The summary statistics can then be screened to remove poor models. Following this more detailed consideration of the thresholded RMSE and visual inspection of the model hydrographs (particularly focusing on the timing of the rising limbs) can be used to select a final model. The selection of this model should also consider the required forecast lead time, it may be acceptable to trade off the quality of the forecast for increased lead time but this is often better assessed after data assimilation.

Table 2: Summaries of the model fit

Value	Formula	Description
Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)	$\sqrt{\frac{\sum_t \eta_t^2}{T}}$	Summary of errors on the same scale as the observed data
Rt2	$R_t^2 = \max \left(1 - \frac{\sum_t \eta_t^2}{\sum_t (y_t - \bar{y})^2}, 0 \right)$	Fraction of the variance of the observed data explained. Values approaching 1 are preferred.
YIC	$\log \left(\sum_i \frac{\Sigma_{ii}}{\theta_i} \right) + \log(1 - R_t^2)$	An information criteria the trades of the indentifiability of the parameters (first term) with the model performance (second term). On a log scale, more negative values are to be preferred.
Thresholded RMSE	$\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t \in y_t > x} \eta_t^2}{\#(y_t > x)}}$	RMSE computed based only time steps where the observed output is greater than the threshold

Data Assimilation

A very important aspect of improving flood forecasts when knowledge of both inputs and appropriate models is subject to error (and uncertainty) is the use of data assimilation or adaptive forecasting. In what follows we consider the assimilation of observations of the output to improve the future forecasts. The structure of the hydrological models used in FloodForT indicates that forecasts at lead times within the catchment lag d can be generated with observed input data. Forecasts at longer lead times require the use of forecast input data. If determinist forecasts, ideally revised every time step are available (e.g. a point summary of a probabilistic DBM model forecast) they can be substituted for the unknown inputs and similar techniques to those used below utilised (see the following section). In more complex situations where there are ensemble forecasts of the input are not considered here (but see Smith and Beven 2010; Smith et al. 2011).

The FloodForT models can be cast within a general state space framework for non-linear models (e.g. Liu and Gupta 2007). The assimilation of observations of the output variable and generation of future forecasts consists of a filtering problem with components. The first is deriving the probability distribution of the states at time $t+1$ given their distribution at time t and new pair of observations (y_{t+1}, u_{t+1-d}) . The second is to evaluate the predictive distribution of an observation n steps ahead by mapping of the stochastic noise terms given the initial distribution of the model states.

In the FloodForT toolbox an alternative strategy is adopted whereby data is assimilated to improve the deterministic forecast of the model with uncertainty in the forecast being represented by a quantile regression. Experience suggests that in this type of application, where the effective input can be computed from observed data, a state space formulation of the linear transfer function embedded in a simple predictor-corrector implementation of the linear Kalman filter performs well in assimilating the data to improve the forecasts. Within FloodForT it is presumed that the system covariance is at a steady state therefore only Kalman Gains require estimation rather than accounting for the full covariance matrices. Note this approximation breaks down close to the in initialisation point and also during periods of missing output data.

To implement this we introduce the state vector \mathbf{x} whose elements represent the responses of each of the paths. Suppose $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1} = (\hat{x}_{t-1,1}, \dots, \hat{x}_{t-1,n})$ is our estimate of the expected value of the states after observing the data up to time step $t-1$. Evolving the model forward in time results in the prediction of the expected value of the states at the next time step; $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$; made up of

$$\hat{x}_{t+1|i,t} = \alpha_i \hat{x}_{t,i} + \beta_i f_{t+1-d} u_{t+1-d} \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

The deterministic prediction of the output at this time step after data assimilation is given by

$$\hat{y}_{t+1|t} = \sum_i \hat{x}_{t+1|i,t} \quad (6)$$

Forecasts at longer lead times as generated by repeated application of Equations (5) and (6).

After observing the output at time $t+1$ the states may be corrected by the formula

$$\hat{x}_{t+1,i} = \hat{x}_{t+1|i,t} + K_i (y_{t+1} - \hat{y}_{t+1|t}) \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

where the K_i are the estimated Kalman gains.

Applying this computational scheme at every time step results in the generation of the forecasts whose values are conditioned upon all the data available at the time the forecast was issued.

Forecast Uncertainty

The uncertainty in the forecast is estimated by a quantile regression based up on the observed pairs of $(y_t, \hat{y}_{t|t-f})$ for each forecast lead time f . This handles the uncertainty arising from all the sources noted earlier and not accounted for by the data assimilation in a lumped fashion. A number of quantile regression techniques have been used in hydrology (see Weerts et al. 2011 and references within). The FloodForT methodology estimates the quantile regression following the non-

parametric approach outlined in Yu (1999) where the initial smoothing is based on utilising the nearest (in terms of $\hat{y}_{i|t-f}$) 10% of the data points.

Installing FloodForT

FloodForT is available as a package for the R statistical software at <http://waternumbers.co.uk>. The latest version of FloodForT will be available as either a *.tar.gz or *.zip file depending upon your operating system. In this section, the file is referred to as <FloodForT>. In the following procedures, it is assumed that the target machine has full internet access and has R already installed. FloodForT supports R version 3.1.1 and later. Full installation instructions for R can be found at <http://cran.r-project.org> along with details of managing R packages.

Prior to installing the FloodForT package it is suggested that you update all the other R packages on your system. To do this open R and at the command prompt type (on one line)

```
update.packages(repos = "http://cran.rstudio.com")
```

then press enter. Installation of FloodForT starts by installing all the dependancies. To do this enter at the command prompt (on one line)

```
install.packages(c("shiny", "dygraphs", "rhandsontable", "sandwich", "xts"), repos = "http://cran.rstudio.com")
```

then press enter. A further command of

```
install.packages(<path/to/FloodForT>)
```

will then install the FloodForT package.

The "http://cran.rstudio.com" in the above commands can be replaced by the path to any CRAN mirror (see <http://cran.r-project.org> for a list of mirrors).

File Formats

The FloodForT toolbox uses three text file formats for importing observed data and outputting forecasts. These formats are delimited ascii text files which can be readily read into, or created by other software packages.

Observed Data

The first file format is for observations. It takes the form of a delimited text file. Comma, semi-column and tab characters are supported as delimiters. The first line of the file contains column headings. These must include Year, Month, Day, Hour, Minute and Second. The remaining column headings are taken to be the names of the locations at which the data are observed. The order of the columns is not important and names are case sensitive.

The subsequent lines of the file contain the observed data. Each row corresponds to the observations at a time given specified by the values of the Year, Month, Day, Hour, Minute and Second columns. Blank or NaN entries are treated as missing values. Data should be entered in temporal order (oldest to newest) and have an equal amount of time between each set of

observations. Series of weights placed on the observations to be used calibration should also be to be included in this file.

Figure 1 shows an example of a file of this format.

```
Year,Month,Day,Hour,Minute,Second,FriarsCarseQ,HallBridgeQ,CraigdarrochRE,EliockRE
1988,1,1,0,0,0,126.96,NaN,0,0
1988,1,1,1,0,0,120.72,NaN,0,0
1988,1,1,2,0,0,114.89,NaN,0,0
1988,1,1,3,0,0,109.19,NaN,0,0
1988,1,1,4,0,0,103.62,NaN,0,0
1988,1,1,5,0,0,100.79,NaN,0,0
1988,1,1,6,0,0,99.276,NaN,0,0
1988,1,1,7,0,0,98.842,NaN,0,0
```

Figure 1 Snippet of a comma delimited Observed Data file showing the format and use of NaN for missing data.

Forecast Data

The forecasts issued by the model can be output as a delimited text file. Comma, semi-column and tab characters are supported as delimiters. The first row of this file contains the column heading. As well as the Year, Month, Day, Hour, Minute and Second columns which specify the time the forecast was issued for subsequent columns labelled f1, f2, f3,... state whether the forecasts are issued 1,2,3,... time steps ago, see Figure 2 for an example.

Year	Month	Day	Hour	Minute	Second	f1	f2	f3	f4	f5
1988	1	1	0	0	0	112.67	115.05	113.63	114.15	115.33
1988	1	1	1	0	0	118.13	120.15	118.59	120.75	117.35
1988	1	1	2	0	0	125.01	125.14	123.57	125.29	124.01
1988	1	1	3	0	0	129.81	130.55	130.69	129.37	130.40
1988	1	1	4	0	0	126.98	126.86	126.35	126.41	128.40
1988	1	1	5	0	0	123.85	125.31	124.58	124.60	124.96
1988	1	1	6	0	0	120.25	119.15	121.96	120.28	121.11
1988	1	1	7	0	0	129.96	128.71	129.62	127.29	127.43

Figure 2: Example of a tab delimited Forecast Data file showing forecast up to 5 hourly time steps ahead.

ModelBuild

The ModelBuild component of the FloodForT toolbox is designed to be used 'off-line' with historic data to build models that can be deployed for forecasting. The ModelBuild component can be run either from the R package or as a standalone program on windows. When run from the R package the ModelBuild graphical user interface opens in the default web browser. The following instructions are valid for each with screenshots showing the R package version.

Running ModelBuild

Starting ModelBuild

If you have installed the FloodForT R package the ModelBuild component can be run by opening R and typing `library(FloodForT); ModelBuild()` then pressing `enter` at the R command prompt.

For the windows program either double click on the shortcut or select from the start menu.

Shutting ModelBuild

To shut ModelBuild either

1. Close the browser (R package version) or
2. Close the windows program

Note that if running ModelBuild from the R package shutting ModelBuild does not close the R session.

Saving Models

Three outputs can be saved from ModelBuild. The *Save* button available after data is loaded allows you to save the current session of ModelBuild which includes the data used and models estimated. This can be reloaded into ModelBuild to continue the analysis. The *Save Model* button save a model in the appropriate format for use in ModelRun. Details of this and the *Save Forecast* button; which outputs the forecasts in a text file; are given in the Data Analysis section.

General Layout

On starting ModelBuild a welcome screen (Figure 3) is shown. Please read the disclaimer. There are five tabs (Figure 3) which are followed sequentially (left to right) to build a model. These are discussed in the following sections. When available buttons to *Save* the analysis or perform other similar tasks are shown in sidebar at the bottom left of the window. The question mark symbol next to the title in the sidebar links to the appropriate part of the manual for the selected tab.

Figure 3: Welcome screen showing the five tabs and link to the manual

Read Data Tab

The aim of the Read Data tab is to allow the user to load data into ModelBuild, visualise the data and if necessary combine the data to make further variable that may be used in the modelling, for example catchment averaged rainfall.

On first selecting the Read Data tab the user is asked to load the data for the analysis (Figure 4). Clicking the *Browse* button opens a file browser for selection of the file to be loaded. Two file types are acceptable. Files of the type *.rds are presumed to be results previously saved from ModelBuild and are loaded accordingly. All other file types are treated as delimited files or the Observe data type outlined in the File Formats section. Remember to choose the correct delimiter from the options given.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Read Data tab and sidebar showing the location of the browse button and selection of delimiter.

Once a file has been successfully loaded the sidebar of the window changes (Figure 5) to show

1. a date range selector
2. a select box allowing the selection of one or more of the data series that have been uploaded
3. a *Scale Data* check box

On selecting the one or more data series the data are displayed in the *Data Table & Data Plot* subsidiary tabs. Only the data within the date range selected are shown (Figure 5). Selecting the *Scale Data* check box scale each of the variables so it's maximum is 1 and minimum 0. This can be useful for plotting variables on different scales (e.g. rainfall and discharge).

Figure 5: A screen shot a data plot showing (a) the selection of the time period; (b) the selection of variables

The *Combine Data* subsidiary tab (Figure 6) allows up to ten of the available data series to be combined to give a new series. On pressing the *Make New Variable* button the variables are combined by summation using the weights specified which are standardised so they equal 1. Negative and zero weights are ignored.

Figure 6: A screenshot of the Combine Data screen. In this case two variables High.Row.1 and Green.Cl.15 are being combined with equal weights.

Select Data Tab

The Select Data tab (Figure 7) is used to specify the data series used in constructing the model. A weighting series can also be specified (see

The FloodForT methodology section for how this is used). The default specification of *Equal* gives all the residuals an equal weight. Sliders allow the specification of the Calibration and Validation time period. The two periods can overlap (though this is not recommended) and they do not need to be concurrent. As data series are selected they will be plotted in scaled form to show the calibration and validation periods.

Pressing the *Set Calibration Data* button sets the selected values for use in future model estimations. If models have already been estimated and these values do not match those used the model estimates are deleted.

Figure 7: In this example of the Data Select tab the data series KirbystephenPrecip has been selected as the input to a model predicting data series Krby.Stephen.1. The residuals have equal weight.

Model Estimation Tab

Having loaded the data and selected which data series to use for to build the model the Model estimation tab allows the estimation of the forecasting models, without the application of data assimilation. Full details of the terminology used in this section to describe the model can be found in the

The FloodForT methodology section.

The sidebar (Figure 8) allows the specification of the range of models to search in terms of the number of parallel pathways and range of time delays. The *remove minima before fitting* check box specifies whether the minima of the output series should be removed before fitting the model. This is useful if there is an approximately constant output that cannot be attributed to short term input response. A final set of check boxes allow the selection of various forms of input non-linearity. At least one of these should be selected.

On pressing the *Estimate Models* button all the models in the ranges selected are estimated. This may take some time. A progress bar is shown.

Figure 8: An example Model results table sorted by Rt2. In this case the first six models all have an improved Rt2 compared to the other models estimated and negative YIC values similar to those of the other models. These would be studied in further detail for example considering the hydrograph plots to select a suitable model.

Results for the estimated models are shown in the three subsidiary tabs. The *Results Table* tab shows a sortable table of model performance for the calibration period. In general, and subject to visual inspection of the results models with lower RMSE, higher Rt2 and lower YIC during calibration are to be preferred. Note that the YIC is on a log scale and is generally negative. An example analysis is shown in Figure 8. The RMSE and Rt2 are also shown for the validation period allowing a simple split sample comparison to avoid over fitting of the data.

The *Result Plots* tab allows the visual inspection of the model fits. By selecting multiple models in the list provided (see Figure 9) models can be compared. Two types of plot can be viewed. The first is of the simulated hydrograph. The second *Thresholded RMSE* summaries RMSE of the model fit on the time steps at which the observed output is greater than the specified threshold. See Figure 9 for an example analysis.

Figure 9: An example thresholded RMSE plot. The two models selected show similar performance given the uncertainty bounds on the estimates, as shown by error bars.

The *Model Parameters* tab shows both the model parameters, an estimate of their uncertainty and the value of various summaries of the model that can be derived from the parameters. These are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of the model available from the model parameters

Summary Name	Description
Advective Time Delay	Time delay from an input until it response is first seen in the output
Time of Concentration	Expected value of the time taken for an input to appear in the output
Path fractions	Fraction of effective input that passes to each path

Data Assimilation Tab

The *Data Assimilation* tab allows the estimation of the data assimilation scheme for any of the estimated models.

The sidebar (Figure 10) allows the selection of the model. At this point files containing forecast input data can be uploaded. The uploaded forecast files should consist of the either of the following

1. A Forecast Data format file with the variable name matching the input variable selected
2. Multiple Forecast Data format files with variable names corresponding to the variable combined to make the input variable

In the second case the forecasts are automatically combined using the same weights as used to combine the observed data. The forecasts of the input are used to increase the available forecast lead time. The forecast data is matched by timestamp to the original data series allowing for gaps.

On pressing the *Estimate Data Assimilation* the parameters of the data assimilation along with the forecast uncertainty bounds are estimated. This may take some time. A message is displayed until estimation is completed.

Figure 10: The data assimilation tab showing the uncertainty plot for a three time step lead time using a two pathway, three time step time delay model with a power law non-linearity.

A number of plots summarising the forecast performance can be generated. Two the *hydrograph* and *Thresholded RMSE* plots are as presented for the model estimation, except that rather than being plotted for multiple models they can be plotted for multiple forecast lead times.

The *Uncertainty* plot (Figure 10) shows for a selected lead time the uncertainty about a forecast of a given value, summarised by quantiles, along with the calibration data.

The *Movie* plot (Figure 11) allows an animation of the forecasts over a selected time window to be displayed. This allows visualisation of the forecasts as they would be seen by an end user except that where the subsequently observed values of the output are known they are plotted.

For estimated models the *Save Model* button and *Save Forecasts* button are displayed. The *Save Forecasts* button outputs a Forecast Data format file containing the results of the current model. Pressing the *Save Model* button outputs the selected model in a format suitable for use in real time forecasting. In both cases the model is run for the entire available data period prior to saving.

Figure 11: An example of a movie plot showing the selector for end time (a) and start time (b). The probabilistic nature of the forecasts is represented by shaded areas, with darker shading representing a higher probability of occurrence.

References

- Alfieri, L., Smith, P. J., Thielen-del Pozo, J., and Beven, K. J. (2011) A staggered approach to flash flood forecasting case study in the Cevennes region. *Advances in Geosciences*, 29, 13–20, doi:10.5194/adgeo-29-13-2011.
- Beven, K.J.; Romanowicz, R.; Pappenberger, F.; Young, P.C. and Werner, M. (2005) The Uncertainty Cascade in Flood Forecasting. In Balbanis, P.; Lambroso, D. and Samuels, P. (ed) *Innovation, Advances and Implementation of Flood Forecasting Technology*, Proceedings of the ACTIF meeting, Tromsø. Abstract, p.33, paper 9p on CD (ISBN 978-1-898485-12-4).
- Beven, K.J.; Young, P.C.; Leedal, D.T. and Romanowicz, R. (2008) Computationally efficient flood water level prediction (with uncertainty). In Samuels P.; Huntingdon, S.; Allsop, W. and Harrop J. (ed) *Flood Risk Management: Research and Practice*. CRC Press / Balkema, ISBN 978-0-415-48507-4
- Beven, K.; Leedal, D.; Smith, P. and Young P. (2011a) Identification and representation of state dependent nonlinearities in flood forecasting using the DBM methodology. In *System Identification, Environmental Modelling and Control*. Springer.
- Beven, K.J.; Smith, P.J. and Wood, A. (2011b) On the colour and spin of epistemic error (and what we might do about it). *Hydrol. Earth Syst Sc*, 15, 3123-3133
- Frewer, L.J.; Howard, C.; Hedderley, D. and Shepherd, R. (1996) What Determines trust in Information about Food-related Risks? *Risk Analysis*, 16 (4), 473-486
- Ihaka, R and Gentleman, R. (1996) R: A Language for Data Analysis and Graphics. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics*, 5(1), 299-314.
- Leedal, D.; Beven, K.J.; Young, P.C. and Romanowicz, R.J. (2008) Data assimilation and adaptive real-time forecasting of water levels in the Eden catchment, UK. In Samuels P.; Huntingdon, S.; Allsop, W. and Harrop J. (ed) *Flood Risk Management: Research and Practice*. CRC Press / Balkema, ISBN 978-0-415-48507-4
- Lees, M.J.; Young, P.C.; Ferguson, S.; Beven, K.J. and Burns, J. (1994) An adaptive flood warning scheme for the River Nith at Dumfries. In W.W.R. and J. Watts (Eds.), *2nd International Conference on River Flood Hydraulics*. Wiley.
- Liu, Y.Q. and Gupta, H.V. (2007) Uncertainty in hydrologic modelling: Toward an integrated data assimilation framework. *Water Resources Research*, 43, W07401
- Newey, W.K. and West, K.D. (1987) A Simple, Positive Semi-Definite, Heteroskedasticity and Autocorrelation Consistent Covariance Matrix. *Econometrica*, 55, 703–708.
- Penning-Rowsell, E.; Potts, D.; Reynard, N.; Simm J.; Tapsell, S.; Thorne, C. and Wheeler, H. (2008) *The Pitt Review: Lessons learned from the 2007 floods*. Cabinet Office. UK Government [online] http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20100807034701/http://archive.cabinetoffice.gov.uk/pit-review/the-pitt-review/final_report.html [accessed 29th June 2012]

Ratto, M.; Young, P.C.; Romanowicz, R.; Pappenberger, F. and Saltelli, Pagano, A. (2007) Uncertainty, sensitivity analysis and the role of data based mechanistic modeling in hydrology. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.*, 11, 1249–1266

Romanowicz, R.J.; Young, P.C. and Beven, K.J. (2006) Data assimilation and adaptive forecasting of water levels in the River Severn catchment, United Kingdom. *Water Resources Research*, 42(6), W06407.

Romanowicz, R.J.; Young, P.C.; Beven, K.J. and Pappenberger, F. (2008) A data based mechanistic approach to nonlinear flood routing and adaptive flood level forecasting. *Advances in Water Resources*, 31, 1048-1056

Smith, P.; Beven, K.; Tych, W.; Hughes, D.; Coulson, G. and Blair, G. (2008) The provision of site specific flood warnings using wireless sensor networks. In Samuels P.; Huntingdon, S.; Allsop, W. and Harrop J. (ed) *Flood Risk Management: Research and Practice*. CRC Press / Balkema, ISBN 978-0-415-48507-4

Smith P.J. and Beven K.J. (2010) Forecasting river levels during flash floods using Data Based Mechanistic models, online data assimilation and meteorological forecasts. *Proceedings of the British Hydrological Society International Symposium, Newcastle (UK)*.

Smith, P.; Beven, K.; Panziera, L. and Germann, U. (2011) Flash flood forecasting using Data Based Mechanistic models and radar rainfall forecasts. *Proceedings of Weather Radar and Hydrology, IAHS Publication 351*.

Smith, P.J.; Beven, K.J. and Horsburgh, K. (2012a) Data-based mechanistic modelling of tidally affected river reaches for flood warning purposes: an example on the River Dee, UK. *Q.J.R. Meteorol. Soc.* doi: 10.1002/qj.1926

Weerts, A.H.; Winsemius H.C. and Verkade, J.S. (2011) Estimation of predictive hydrological uncertainty using quantile regression: examples from the national flood forecasting system (England and Wales). *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 15(1):255–265

Young, P. (1976) Some Observations On Instrumental Variable Methods Of Time-Series Analysis. *International Journal Of Control*, 23, 593-612

Young, P.C. (2001) Data-based mechanistic modelling and validation of rainfall-flow processes. In Anderson, M.G. and Bates, P.B. (Eds) *Model Validation: Perspectives in Hydrological Science*, Wiley: Chichester, 117-161.

Young, P.C. (2002) Advances in real-time flood forecasting. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London Series A - Mathematical Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 360(1796), 1433-1450.

Young, P.C. (2003) Top-down and data-based mechanistic modelling of rainfall-flow dynamics at the catchment scale. *Hydrological Processes*, 17(11), 2195-2217.

Young, P.C. (2006) Updating Algorithms in Flood Forecasting. FRMRC Research Report UR5 available at: www.floodrisk.org.uk.

Young, P.C. (2011) *Recursive Estimation and Time Series Analysis: An Introduction*. Berlin: Springer Verlag.

Young, P. C. and Beven, K. J. (1994) Data-Based Mechanistic Modeling and the Rainfall-Flow Nonlinearity. *Environmetrics*, 5, 335-363

Young, P.C.; McKenna, P. and Bruun, J. (2001) Identification of non-linear stochastic systems by state dependent parameter estimation. *International Journal of Control*, 74(18), 1837-1857.

Young, P.C. and Garnier, H. (2006) Identification and estimation of continuous-time, data-based mechanistic (DBM) models for environmental systems. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 21, 1055-1072

Young, P. C.; Castelletti, A. and Pianosi, F. (2007) The data-based mechanistic approach in hydrological modelling. In Castelletti, A. and Sessa, R.S. (eds) *Topics on System Analysis and Integrated Water Resource Management*, 27–48. Elsevier: Amsterdam.

Yu, K. (1999) Smoothing regression quantile by combining k-NN estimation with local linear kernel fitting. *Statistica Sinica* 9, 759-774

Zeileis, A. (2004) Econometric Computing with HC and HAC Covariance Matrix Estimators. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 11(10), 1–17. URL <http://www.jstatsoft.org/v11/i10/>.

Change Log

Version	Date	Alterations	Author
v0.1	April 2014	Initial draft	Paul Smith
v0.8	May 2014	Altered to match v0.8. Description of the theory, ModelRun and ResVis added	Paul Smith
v0.9	Sept 2016	Tided to allow for removal of ModelRun and ResVis. Installation instructions added	Paul Smith